

THE USE OF DISCOVERY METHOD IN THE EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF EFFECT OF AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES ON ECOSYSTEM

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Abstract

This study examined the use of discovery method in the effective teaching of agricultural activities on ecosystem. It is a quasi experimental research using pre-test, treatment and post-test method. Data gathered in the study were analyzed using the result of students' score. Result of the study clearly showed that the use of discovery method enhanced students' academic performance. The researcher recommended the use of discovery method for the effective teaching of agricultural activities on ecosystem.

Keywords: *Discovery method, Effective Teaching, Agricultural Activities, Ecosystem*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching approach may differ depending on the complexity and structure of the topics, and learning is most interesting if teachers use the most appropriate method to teach. Nowadays, experimental approach to teaching is fast taking over the traditional "chalk-talk" method, which allows

students to discover concepts on their own this method of learning increases retention, motivate students to learn and encourages group co-operation because it is a teaching technique that involves oral and doing instruction to communicate processes, concepts and facts (Sola and Ojo 2007).

The method of instruction used to teach a particular topic or subject depends on which method will effectively communicate the concept and assures that the learner has learnt (Meyer 1954). He further asserted that various methods are used to teach students different topics and subjects, amongst which are; lecture method, demonstration method, inquiry method, discovery method, question and answer method, among several others. He is of the opinion that the best teaching results from clearly defined objectives, carefully selected materials and the method best suited to the students and teacher's own talent.

Biology, being a natural science requires the employment of an instructional strategy that will enhance effective teaching and meaningful learning of its fundamental concepts (Bello 2011). Discovery method of instruction when used to teach biological concept and principles ensures full participation of the learners and encourages the acquisition of new knowledge. Abimbola (1987) states that discovery as a teaching approach has been in use for several decades; he cited Willoughby (1963) and Bolding (1969) who noted that the discovery teaching methods are related to the teaching methods of Socrates. Skinner (1968) believes that the discovery principle allows student to learn from nature; let him go directly to the facts and to things which are recorded as been observed.

Discovery method requires that the teacher should introduce the topic to be learnt to the students so as to have a fore and basic knowledge about the topic, then left to be in charge of the learning process which is being supervised by the teacher this learning process will be considered from three points of view according to (Bicknell-Holmes & Hoffman, 2000):

- exploration and problem solving
- student determines the sequence and frequency
- integration of new knowledge into the learner's existing knowledge base.

Methodology

A quasi experimental study was conducted on 21 senior secondary II students drawn from three schools in Ilorin metropolis. The students were grouped into three and were taken to the field where they were allowed to learn by discovery. They were initially subjected to pre-test assessment before learning and post-test assessment after learning by discovery to determine if they have acquired new knowledge.

Table 1: Pre-test assessment result

Group 1	Score out of 10 Marks	Group 2	Score out of 10 marks	Group 3	Score out of 10 Marks
Student 1	2	Student 8	3	Student 15	4
Student 2	3	Student 9	4	Student 16	2
Student 3	4	Student 10	2	Student 17	4
Student 4	1	Student 11	2	Student 18	3
Student 5	3	Student 12	4	Student 19	2
Student 6	2	Student 13	5	Student 20	2
Student 7	4	Student 14	3	Student 21	1

Procedure/Learning Activities

Students of senior secondary school II, were divided into three groups of seven students each.

Step 1

The teacher introduces the topic by explaining agricultural activities:

- bush burning
- tillage
- application of fertilizer and herbicide;

Step 2

The students observed the initial condition on the farm site before embarking on the various agricultural activities stated above. They were left to take note of the flora and fauna that exist on that farm, which are as shown below;

Table 2: List of flora and fauna on the farm site

<u>Animals</u>	<u>Plants</u>
Birds	Shrubs
Lizard	Grasses
Insects	Lichen
Snake	Trees
Rats	Mushrooms etc.
Centipede etc.	

Step 3

Each of the students' group separately observed the effects of one of these activities on the ecological system.

Group one: observes bush burning

Group two: tillage activities

Group three: application of fertilizer and herbicide

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Table 3: Activities of the groups and their discovery

Group	Activity	Discovery	Teacher	New knowledge acquired
One	The students burned the bush on the farm site	Plants were destroyed, animals that were not killed were displaced from their natural habitat of nests and burrows.	Explains that nutrients in the soil will be affected, likewise micro-organisms such as nitrogen fixing bacteria	The students learnt that bush burning destroys plants in the soil, animals are displaced from their natural habitat, exposing the farm to erosion and ultra violet rays of the sun
Two	Tillage; the soil was over turned	Organisms living in the sub-surface e.g ants,	The displaced organisms and their larvae	Students learned that organisms live beneath the

Group one: burned the bush to clear the farmland for cultivation, they saw that plants were destroyed and animals were sent away from their natural habitat. They acquired new knowledge that bush burning causes displacement of animals from their natural habitat thus, exposing them to danger of predation. Plants were also destroyed causing imbalance in the

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		Centipede, termite etc, were exposed fur to the destruction of their natural homes.	Have been exposed to danger of predation and desiccation.	Earth's surface and affecting fixing of organic matter in the soil for plants and loosening of the soil for aeration.
Three	Application of fertilizer and herbicide to crop	Fertilizer (artificial; NPK) makes the crop blossom and grow well, while application of herbicide destroys plants except for the desired crop	Although fertilizer has beneficial effect on the crop but may affect some fauna and near by streams adversely, likewise the herbicides.	Students learned that fertilizer and herbicides are agrochemicals that have both beneficial and adverse effects on the ecosystem depending on the purpose for which they are meant.

Table 4: Post-test assessment result

Group 1	Score out of 10 Marks	Group 2	Score out of 10 marks	Group 3	Score out of 10 marks
Student 1	8	Student 8	9	Student 15	10
Student 2	7	Student 9	8	Student 16	8
Student 3	8	Student 10	9	Student 17	8
Student 4	7	Student 11	9	Student 18	9
Student 5	8	Student 12	10	Student 19	9
Student 6	9	Student 13	10	Student 20	7
Student 7	8	Student 14	10	Student 21	9

Discussion

The pre-test and post-test assessment results in table 1 and table 4 show that there is a significant change in the knowledge of the students before and after the discovery teaching-learning process. This showed that new knowledge has been acquired.

The use of discovery method of instruction has been seen to aid students in acquiring new knowledge by "doing" based on the initial basic knowledge that they have and the basic knowledge teacher has imparted on them. The students in the three groups were separately left alone to interact amongst themselves by exchanging views and ideas, with a little more guidance from the teacher additional knowledge is acquired.

Group one: burned the bush to clear the farmland for cultivation, they saw that plants were destroyed and animals were sent away from their natural habitat. They acquired new knowledge that bush burning causes displacement of animals from their natural habitat thus, exposing them to danger of predation. Plants were also destroyed causing imbalance in the

Food chain of the ecosystem, and that the farm was also exposed to erosion and harsh intensity of ultra violet rays.

Group two: cultivation of the farm by tillage upturns the sub-soil over the top soil exposing the ants, termites and worms where they soften the soil and introduces organic matters. The new knowledge acquired is that aeration of the soil, addition of organic matter to the soil will be affected, hence reducing soil fertility and the organisms will lose their homes.

Group three: After fertilizer and herbicide application on the farm the new knowledge learnt was that it had dual effects. The fertilizer improves the plant growth, likewise the residue has adverse effect when it seeps into rivers and streams affecting the aquatic lives. The herbicide kills weed but the residue also affects animals, aquatic organisms and other economic plants that are not the target and even the crop plants grown.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The discovery method ignites students' enthusiasm for learning biology by discovering information that helps them to increase their knowledge of the subject matter after being given basic knowledge by the teacher. It gives them the confidence and the power to independently discover, question, analyze, and conquer new ideas. The method cannot be completely employed independently, but effectively practiced in conjunction with other teaching methods such as lecture method, chalk-talk and experimenting for basic knowledge of the topic and further guidance by the teacher. Therefore, the integration of discovery method in Group work is recommended in the teaching and learning of biology and sciences in general, because of high level of interaction and exchange of ideas.

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